

Role of Physical Education, Sports for Fitness, Health and Wellness

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Abstract:

Fitness plays a critical role in our overall health today, most of the health disorders are a result of an unfit body and bad food habits. Problems like body ache and muscular pain are the most common consequences of sloth lifestyle. Inadequate exercise leads to weight gain and obesity. Living healthier life can not only extend our life, it can also improve the quality. Feeling physically better and having control over our own life can greatly increase our mental health as well. Although there are some aspects of physical and mental health that are beyond an individual's (and science's) control, there are many things that people can do to improve their quality of life. Good health has traditionally been viewed as freedom from disease; thus, if we not sick, were considered healthy. This perspective is changing. While everyone agrees that the absence of illness is one part of being healthy, it doesn't indicate whether we are in a state of well-being. Lack of physical activity is mainly responsible for much health complication in children and youngsters. To prevent these health troubles, a proper fitness is essential for everyone. Fitness should be a key component in anybody's life simply for the fact that it makes you feel better. Wellness, as a state of health, is closely associated with our lifestyle. Each person has a responsibility to provide for such health essentials as good nutrition, proper weight control, exercise, and controlling of risk factor such as smoking, alcohol and drug abuse.

Keywords: Physical Education, Sports, Fitness, Health and Wellness.

Introduction:

Aristotle had said that "man is a social animal and mans birth in society brings with it the absolute need of society itself". Physical Education & Sports activities are mostly group activities offering man opportunity for socialization & development of social qualities in individuals & sociology with us knowledge of human relations in society & various problems arising out of such relations can guide us properly for achieving social objectives of organizing Physical Education & Sports Programmer. Physical Education activities bring individuals of different economic states, caste, religions & social customs etc. on one common platform when they interact with other members

of the group. Through such contacts they often develop friendship sympathy, love & affection for others such feelings are particularly noticeable in victories, defeats, & accidents etc. In this field sharing & caring qualities are often called for & displayed a regular exposure to such situations in the sports world helps in developing sympathetic attitudes in participants.

Overall Important:

1. Physical wellbeing, personal life skills, social bane it is the most important bane it is are of an individual nature and less community focused also important are opportunities from sport and recreation

- leadership skills and ability to deal with stress.
2. Physical wellbeing Emotional wellbeing social and friendships life skills being part of the community improving the community.
 3. Nine out of Ten people believe that being involved in sports and recreation has a positive import.
 4. The grass-roots sports and active recreation sector plays a care role in promoting healthy & vibrant communications.
 5. Sports & active recreation plays a much broader role than just providing physical activities opportunities.
 6. It weaves the social fabric on which our communities are built, promoter healthy & wellbeing reduces to economic impact of life style related diseases, provide employment opportunities and is a vehicle by which major events can be delivered.

Sports and Recreation:

The study found 20 ways Sports & recreation benefits for people:

1. The overwhelming response was that sport & recreation delivered substantial benefits individual familiar and the community
2. The Improves physical wellbeing
3. Teacher fair play & respect builder & self esteem
4. Provide opportunity to meet other
5. Develop self-discipline & Commitment
6. Life-skills such as respect for other
7. Provide a sense of Community Builds communication skills
8. Builder stronger family relationship community pride
9. Provides support networks & builds

10. Develops leadership skills improve ability to care with stress or difficult situations creator tolerant communities
11. Reduce anti-social behavior in the community makes the community safer crates.

Tolerance:

In games very often situations arise when conditions may not be favorable to an individual. An incorrect umpiring decision, an undesirable action or foul committed by an opponent can arouse passions physical Education programmes teach a provocations & respect the decisions even if they are wrong such situation develop in individuals the attitude of tolerance

Patience:

Success cannot be achieved in life through short cuts or by being impatience patience & perseverance or continuous hard work are keys to success in all walles of life patience during training for various games is essential because skills are learned slowly patience is often called for in game situation. Impatience in such situations does not help. If often result sin making mistakes. Take for example the game patience during prolonged rallies pays. An impatient player by switching over to attack often commits faults & looser the game an impatient athlete can easily burn himself out in long distance races. Therefore development of patience in games & sports. An help an individual in like Games & Sports are good means of developing patience participation & proper direction in games & sports by keeping in view the common. Objectives can help in developing the social trait.

Sportsmanship:

Obedience of rules, fair play courtesy, modesty etc. are some of the qualities of sportsmanship by curbing indiscipline on the play

fields & encouraging fair play & obedience of rules, Physical Education programmes help in developing sportsmanship.

Definitions:

Wellness:

The term wellness was first used by a physician named Halbert L. Dunn, who published a small booklet entitled "High level Wellness" in 1961. Dr. Dunn saw wellness as a lifestyle approach for pursuing elevated states of physical and psychological well-being. He described it as a disciplined commitment to personal mastery.

Fitness:

1. "Physical fitness is defined as "a set of attributes that people have or achieve that relates to the ability to perform physical activity" (USDHHS, 1996).
2. Being physically fit has been defined as "the ability to carry out daily tasks with vigor and alertness, without undue fatigue and with ample energy to enjoy leisure-time pursuits and to meet unforeseen emergencies"
3. Fitness means Improved Physiological State that leads to Improved Health and Longevity.

Types of Fitness:

There are two types of fitness (A) Health Related Fitness (HRF). (B) Skill Related Fitness (SRF)

Health Related Fitness:

1. **Cardiovascular Ability:** Body's ability to take in oxygen, deliver it to cells use it at a cellular level to create energy for physical work - endurance, strength, power.
2. **Muscular Ability:** Analysis of muscular capability endurance, Strength, power.
3. **Flexibility:** ability of a joint to move through a specific range of motion.

4. **Body Composition:** Proportion of fat-free mass to fat mass.

Skill Related Fitness:

1. Agility, 2. Balance, 3. Coordination, 4. Speed, 5. Power, 6. Reaction time

Need and Importance of Fitness:

We all know that being physically fit is good for us, but exactly what are the needs of physical fitness? why is physical fitness important?

Need:

1. Effective Work
2. Good Health
3. Face Emergencies

Importance:

Fitness is important for people of all age groups.

1. Overall Health
2. Boosts Energy
3. Weight Reduction
4. You'll keep your bones strong
5. You'll sleep better
6. Strong Build
7. Mental Strength
8. Personality Development.

Effects of Physical Fitness:

1. Sedentary lifestyle
2. Smoking
3. Alcohol
4. Obesity
5. Insufficient sleep, and
6. Non-prescribed pharmaceuticals.

Healthy Lifestyles:

1. Regular physical activity
2. Eating well
3. Managing stress
4. Avoiding bad habits
5. Practicing safe sex
6. Learning first aid

7. Seeking medical advice, 8. Protecting the environment.

Benefits of Fitness:

- Improves sleep, Improves body composition, Increases bone density, Decreases risk of injury, promotes joint stability and strength, Increases BMR, Increases Immunity, Improves Circulatory system health, Decreases risk of disease (cancer, type II diabetes), Assists in stress management, Decreases depression, Improves self-image, Lose Excess Body Fat. Increases Energy, Improves Athletic Performance, Injury and Disease Prevention, Increase muscle mass and bone strength.

Effects of being physically fit:

- Wonderful stress reliever, Improves flexibility, Increases energy levels and stamina, Helps regulate your appetite, Postpones the process of aging, Enhances quality of life, Helps you look better, Helps you sleep better.

Mental benefits of physical fitness:

- Releases endorphins which are responsible for our psychological well being and also help in reducing pain, Increases brain power by increasing serotonin levels in our brains, which leads to improved mental clarity and Boosts self confidence, improves mood, and relieves symptoms of depression, Benefits of Wellness, high self-esteem and a positive outlook, a foundation philosophy and a sense of purpose, a strong sense of personal responsibility, a good sense of humor and plenty of fun in life, a concern for others and a respect for the environment, a conscious commitment to

personal excellence, a sense of balance and an integrated lifestyle, freedom from addictive behaviors of a negative or health-inhibiting nature, a capacity to cope with whatever life presents and to continue to learn grounded in reality highly conditioned and physically fit, a capacity to love and an ability to nurture, a capacity to manage life demands and communicate effectively.

Fitness achievements:

There are many ways to achieve fitness. For fitness one should perform physical activities regularly.

1. Performing Yogasanas & pranayama
2. Brisk walking for at least 20 min
3. Jogging and running
4. Swimming
5. Cycling
6. Playing various sports & games.

Healthy lifestyles:

1. Good food habits
2. Avoiding drugs, alcohol, smoking, etc.
3. Daily hygiene & sanitation.

Conclusion:

The benefits of fitness & wellness make us to live much healthier life. It helps us to deal successfully with the difficult situations arising in our day to day life. Today every one knows that life became more faster and if we want to go with that speed we should be fit physically as well as mentally.

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